

Student profiles of change in a university course: A complex dynamical systems perspective. Supplementary material

December 14, 2022

Authored by Poquet, O., Jovanovic, J., Pardo, A.

1 Introduction

This document includes supplementary information related to the following study by Oleksandra Poquet, Jelena Jovanovic, and Abelardo Pardo, published in 2023, titled "Student profiles of change in a university course: A complex dynamical systems perspective" that is included in the proceedings of LAK23: 13th International Learning Analytics and Knowledge Conference (LAK 2023), March 13–17, 2023, Arlington, TX, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA.

2 Normalised entropy

Normalised entropy was calculated as follows:

$$ENTR_N = \frac{ENTR}{MAX_ENTR} \quad (1)$$

$$ENTR = - \sum_{l=l_{\min}}^N p(l) \ln p(l) \quad (2)$$

$$MAX_ENTR = \frac{ENTR}{-1 * \log(\frac{1}{DL_{max}})} \quad (3)$$

where $ENTR$ is Shannon's entropy,
 l is the length of a diagonal line,
 $p(l)$ is the probability of a diagonal line of length l ,
and DL_{max} is maximal diagonal line.

3 Latent Class Modelling Plots

The paper reports summary statistics for means and standard errors for the latent growth curves. Below we report raw data plots.

Figure 1: Trajectory plots for class 1

Figure 2: Trajectory plots for class 2

Figure 3: Trajectory plots for class 3